

Use of mustard cake as adsorbent for adsorption of patent-blue dye from aqueous solution and its desorption studies

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Abstract : The adsorption of patent-blue on de-oiled mustard was investigated to assess the possible use of this adsorbent for the processing of dye industry waste water. The efficiency of de-oiled mustard in the dye colour sorption was compared with activated carbon i.e. charcoal. The influence of various factors such as adsorbent dose, contact time, pH, adsorbate concentration, particle size, temperature on the adsorption capacity has been studied by batch experiments. The adsorption studies revealed that the ongoing adsorption validates both Langmuir and Freundlich adsorption isotherms at temperatures 40, 50 and 60 °C. Thermodynamic parameters such as ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° for the adsorption process were calculated. Desorption profile revealed that a significant portion of the dye (92%) was recovered by using 1.0 M NaOH as eluting agent.

Keywords : Adsorption, de-oiled mustard (DOM), patent-blue, desorption.

Introduction

Effluents from dye processing, textiles and pulp and paper industries into water bodies contaminates the environment. The removal of colour from the textile dyeing wastewater has been brought under the purview of legal and regulatory requirements. Because of their high water solubility and colour, dyes impart taste and odour problems to drinking water supplied, even at the part per billion levels. Before discharging dyeing industry waste water into the natural water streams, it needs to be treated. Among the several known physical, chemical and biological methods which are in use for waste water treatment, adsorption technique is the most widely used process. The adsorption by activated carbon¹, i.e. charcoal has become the water industry's standard for the reclamation of municipal and industrial waste water to a potable water quality. Activated carbon is quite expensive and the tedious procedure for its regeneration led many workers to search for low cost potential adsorbents². Some new adsorbents which have been tried with varying success are Crab shell, peanut hull pellets, petcolar felt-seath of palm,

cornstarch, soyabean hull and sugar beat fiber, rice husk, spent grain, saw dust etc.³.

The present study deals with the removal of patent-blue dye from wastewater by adsorption technique, where de-oiled mustard (agricultural by product) is converted into a cheap adsorbent and its efficiency is compared with activated carbon.

Structure of patent-blue dye

Experimental

Materials and methods :

The water soluble patent-blue dye (molecular

formula $C_{27}H_{31}N_2O_7S_2 \cdot \frac{1}{2}Ca$, molecular weight 566.68) was obtained from M/s Merck and its 0.01 M stock solution was prepared in double distilled water. Solutions of desired concentrations of the dye was prepared from stock solution where double distilled water was used for necessary dilutions. All reagents used in the present work were of analytical grade.

Adsorbent activated carbon was also purchased from M/s Merck. All pH measurements were carried out with a decibel DB 1011 digital pH meter, fitted with a glass electrode. Absorbance measurements were recorded spectrophotometrically on a Spectronic 20 D+ Thermospectronic spectrophotometer over the wave length range 200–800 nm.

Small size de-oiled mustard was collected from local oil mills, which was crushed, thoroughly washed with distilled water and then dried in an oven. The dried material was then treated with hydrogen peroxide solution for 24 h to oxidize adhering organic impurities. Then the resultant solution is dried at 110 °C for 1 h in vacuum oven. The dried adsorbent is then grounded and sieved to desired particle sizes such as <106, 106–125, 125–180, 180–212, 212–250, 250–300, >300 MIC mesh size and stored in separate vacuum dessicator for further studies. The physical characteristics of the mustard cake prepared as adsorbent are 46% proteins, 7.05% oil.

Adsorption studies of the adsorbents charcoal and de-oiled mustard were performed by batch technique at 40, 50 and 60 °C. A series of volumetric flasks containing equal volumes (30 mL) of adsorbate solutions at varying concentrations were employed at desired pH. An optimized amount of adsorbent of particle size 125–180 MIC is then added in each flask and intermittently agitated for a suitable contact time. Then the adsorbent and adsorbate separated through Whatmann filter paper No.1 and the filtrate is analysed spectrophotometrically at λ_{max} 639.2 nm.

Regeneration is the most significant aspect of the adsorption study. Continuing emphasis was being placed on waste minimization, recovery and reuse. Studies were carried out on column. Suitable adsorbent containing adsorbed dye is packed in a column, suitable eluent is passed through the column repeatedly at intervals till maximum colour is eluted out. Then the

amount of dye desorbed was estimated spectrophotometrically. Thus desorption studies help in the recycling and regeneration of the spent adsorbent and the dye.

Results and discussion

Effect of adsorbent dose :

To optimize the adsorbent dose for the removal of patent-blue from its aqueous solutions, adsorption was carried out at three different temperatures (40, 50 and 60 °C). The dose of adsorbent for charcoal was varied from 0.06 to 0.26 g/L and for de-oiled mustard from 2.5 to 17.5 g/L at pH 3.0 and adsorbate concentration ($6 \times 10^{-5} M$). The results are presented in Figs.1(a) and (b). It was observed that at all temperatures, for charcoal adsorption increases from 0.06 to 0.20 g/L and for de-oiled mustard it increases from 2.5 to 10 g/L. Thus adsorption increases with the increase in dose of adsorbent due to the availability of more binding sites for adsorption. However, further increase in the dose of adsorbent did not effect the uptake capacity, because of the unavailability of the adsorbate.

Fig. 1(a). Plots of adsorbent dose vs adsorption of patent-blue over charcoal.

Fig. 1(b). Plots of adsorbent dose vs adsorption of patent-blue over de-oiled mustard.

Fig. 2(a). Plot of contact time vs adsorption of patent-blue over charcoal.

Fig. 2(b). Plot of contact time vs adsorption of patent-blue over de-oiled mustard.

The adsorption experiments were carried out at different contact time with fixed adsorbent dose (0.2 g/L of charcoal and 5.0 g/L of de-oiled mustard), temperature (60 °C), pH 3.0 and concentration 6×10^{-5} M [Figs. 2(a) and (b)]. It is clear from figure that optimum time 30 min and 5 h for charcoal and de-oiled mustard respectively is sufficient for removal of dye. The increase in adsorption of patent-blue with increase in agitation time may be due to increased intraparticle diffusion occurring at long shaking time.

Fig. 3. Plots of pH vs % colour removal of patent-blue over charcoal and de-oiled mustard.

Fig. 4. Plots of adsorbate concentration vs adsorption of patent-blue over charcoal and de-oiled mustard

Fig. 5. Plots of particle size of adsorbent vs adsorption of patent-blue over charcoal and de-oiled mustard

The influence of pH was studied over the pH range 2.62 to 9.13 and pH profiles are shown in Fig. 3. It is apparent that in both cases adsorption increases with decrease in pH. For charcoal, maximum uptake of dye was at pH 2.62 and colour removal was 95% and for de-oiled mustard at pH 2.62 colour removal was 93%, which indicate that positive charge develops on the surface of an adsorbent in an acidic medium, resulting in the higher adsorption of dye.

For observing the effect of concentration of the adsorbate, the dye concentration range of 1.0×10^{-5} to 9.0×10^{-5} M was selected at temperature (60 °C) and contact time (20 min for charcoal and 5 h for de-oiled mustard) as shown in Fig. 4. Here, adsorption decreases with increase in concentration of adsorbate, due to decrease in readily available vacant sites as dye concentration is increased.

The adsorption studies were carried out at seven different particle sizes which were <106, 106–125, 125–180, 180–212, 212–250, 250–300 and >300 MIC (Fig. 5). It can be observed that as the particle size decreases, the adsorption of the dye increases.

Fig. 6(a). Plot of effect of temperature on adsorption of patent-blue over charcoal.

Fig. 6(b). Plot of effect of temperature on adsorption of patent-blue over de-oiled mustard.

Maximum adsorption for charcoal is 97% and for de-oiled mustard is 72% at a mesh size <106 MIC. This is due to larger surface area associated with smaller particles.

Adsorption studies were carried out at 40, 50 and 60 °C for charcoal and de-oiled mustard as exhibited in Figs. 6(a) and (b). It is apparent that with both the adsorbents, adsorption increases with increase in temperature, signifying the process to be endothermic in nature.

Adsorption isotherm : Adsorption isotherm is useful in describing how solutes interrelate with the adsorbent and so is critical in optimizing the use of adsorbents. Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms were used to analyze the adsorption isotherm results.

Fig. 7(a). Langmuir adsorption isotherm of patent-blue over charcoal.

Fig. 7(b). Langmuir adsorption isotherm of patent-blue over de-oiled mustard.

Langmuir isotherms has been found to be a successful application in many real sorption processes⁴. The basic assumption is once a dye molecule occupies a site, no further sorption can take place at that site. The saturated monolayer curve can be represented by the equation,

$$\frac{1}{q_e} = \frac{1}{Q^0} + \frac{1}{bQ^0C_e} \quad (1)$$

where q_e is the amount adsorbed (mol/g), C_e is the equilibrium concentration of the adsorbate (mol/g) and Q^0 and b are the Langmuir constants related to maximum adsorption capacity and energy of adsorption respectively. When $1/q_e$ is plotted against $1/C_e$, a straight

Table 1. Langmuir constants for the adsorption of patent-blue
Langmuir constants

Temp. (°C)	Charcoal			De-oiled mustard		
	b (mol g ⁻¹)	Q^0 (L mol ⁻¹)	R_L	b (mol g ⁻¹)	Q^0 (L mol ⁻¹)	R_L
40	1.264	5.8	0.930	0.486	1.8	0.451
50	2.156	5.1	0.885	0.686	1.7	0.368
60	2.466	5.0	0.871	0.535	1.4	0.427

Fig. 8(a). Freundlich adsorption isotherm of patent-blue over charcoal.

Fig. 8(b). Freundlich adsorption isotherm of patent-blue over de-oiled mustard.

line with slope $1/bQ^{\circ}$ at temperature 40, 50 and 60 °C is obtained [Figs. 7(a) and (b)], indicating that the adsorption of dye on charcoal and de-oiled mustard follows the Langmuir isotherm. The values of 'b' and Q° are tabulated in Table 1.

The essential characteristics of isotherm can be expressed in terms of dimensionless constant separation factor R_L , which is expressed by the following equation,

$$R_L = \frac{1}{1 + bC_0} \quad (2)$$

where C_0 is the initial concentration of dye and b is the Langmuir constant. The parameter indicate the shape

Fig. 9. Desorption profile of patent-blue from de-oiled mustard using different concentrations of NaOH.

of isotherm to be irreversible ($R_L = 0$), favourable ($0 < R_L < 1$), linear ($R_L = 1$) and unfavourable ($R_L > 1$). It is clear from Table 1, that the R_L values are less than unity, thereby confirming favourable adsorption process.

The linear form of Freundlich equation is represented as :

$$\log q_e = \log K_f + \frac{1}{n} \log C_e \quad (3)$$

where K_f and n are Freundlich constants related to adsorption capacity and adsorption intensity respectively. Figs. 8(a) and (b) were used to calculate the K_f and n and their values are listed in Table 2.

Thermodynamic parameters : Thermodynamic parameters for the adsorption of patent-blue dye on charcoal and de-oiled mustard were calculated using following equations and their values are given in Table 3,

$$\Delta G^{\circ} = -RT \ln b' \quad (4)$$

$$\ln b_2/b_1 = (\Delta H^{\circ}/R) (T_2 - T_1/T_2T_1) \quad (5)$$

$$\Delta S^{\circ} = -(\Delta G^{\circ} - \Delta H^{\circ})/T \quad (6)$$

where ΔG° is change in free energy, ΔH° is the change in enthalpy and ΔS° is the change in entropy, b' , b_1 and b_2 are the Langmuir constants at 40, 50 and 60 °C

Table 2. Freundlich constants for the adsorption of patent-blue
Freundlich constants

Temp. (°C)	Charcoal			De-oiled mustard		
	K_f	n	R_L	K_f	n	R_L
40	2.00	0.875	0.950	63.11	0.75	0.347
50	4.01	0.703	0.959	74.80	0.33	0.923
60	4.35	0.687	0.960	880.60	0.23	0.634

respectively. The negative value of ΔG° indicate that adsorption of patent-blue dye on both adsorbents is spontaneous. The positive value of ΔH° , confirms the endothermic nature of adsorption. The value of ΔS° shows a decrease which was due to the enhancement of ordering of the dye molecules on both adsorbents, which reflects the affinity of adsorbents towards dye.

Table 3. Thermodynamic parameters of patent-blue with charcoal and de-oiled mustard

Adsorbent	ΔG° (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔH° (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS° (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)
Charcoal	-264.7	5267	-15.98
De-oiled mustard	-814.5	9657	-33.4

COD of adsorbed dye solution gets considerably reduced after adsorption on charcoal and mustard cake. COD of the solution after adsorption shows significant decrease from 1270 mg/L to 262 mg/L for charcoal and from 1270 mg/L to 265 mg/L for mustard cake.

Desorption studies : After determining the sorption profile, the possibility of recycling the adsorbent is investigated. Adsorption column chromatography method⁵ is adopted. 400 mg of de-oiled mustard is packed in the column. Length of the packing in the column was set upto 4.5 cm. Three different concentrations of NaOH i.e. 1, 0.1 and 0.01 M as eluent were used which was passed at a flow rate of 5 mL/min and fractions collected after every 10 min, were analysed spectrophotometrically. It is seen from Fig. 9, with 1.0 M NaOH 92% of dye was desorbed from de-oiled mustard, with 0.1 M NaOH, 74% was desorbed and on further decreasing the concentration to 0.01 M only 60% was desorbed.

Conclusion :

Mustard cake is found to be effective adsorbent for the removal of dye. Its adsorption capacity though not

comparable with that of activated carbon but is found to be reasonably good. Since mustard cake is cost-effective, it can be tried as adsorbent to remove colour from industrial effluents. Being a waste product it provides solution for solid-waste management and solves the problem of disposal.

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